

Automating Home Controls Using Google Assistant

Dr.Suhas S K , Associate Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering S.E.A College of Engineering and Technology Bangalore

Deepa Gowda N Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering S.E.A College of Engineering and Technology Bangalore

Mrs K Revathi , Assistant Professor , Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering , S E.A College of Engineering and Technology , Bangalore

Dr. Pradeep kumar N S, Professor, Department of ECE, SEA College of Engineering and Technology, Bangalore

Dr. Girish H, Professor, Department of ECE, Cambridge Institute of Technology

Abstract— *The increasing adoption of home automation systems has revolutionized the way we interact with our living spaces, significantly enhancing comfort and overall quality of life. The convenience and efficiency offered by these systems are driving their rapid growth and widespread attention. This paper delves into the development of a Smart Home Automation System leveraging the Internet of Things (IoT) in conjunction with Google Assistant. By integrating cloud networking and wireless communication, this system empowers users to remotely control various home appliances, such as lights and fans, through voice commands or smartphones. The ability to store data in the cloud further enriches the user experience, providing not only convenience but also a heightened standard of living characterized by luxury and ease. The proposed system seamlessly combines the use of Adafruit and IFTTT (If This Then That) services to deliver a cohesive and intuitive user experience. By leveraging these technologies, the system offers an intelligent solution that adapts to modern lifestyle demands, allowing for effortless automation and control of household appliances. This research highlights the potential of IoT-driven home automation to transform everyday routines, making homes smarter, more responsive, and ultimately contributing to a more connected and comfortable living environment.*

Keywords- *IOT, Automation, LPG, LDR, DHT, Relays*

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, Smart Home Automation Systems encompass a range of technological capabilities that enable easy and intelligent control of household electrical appliances, enhancing convenience, security, and energy efficiency. These systems allow users to remotely manage their home environments through computers or smartphones. The Google Assistant-based home automation framework leverages PCs and mobile devices to control home appliances via the internet from anywhere. With the rise of IoT applications, smart home systems are pivotal in the development of smart cities globally. Our goal is to design a cost-effective, flexible, and scalable wireless smart home system that integrates wireless communication and remote control. Despite the rapid advancement of technology, there is still a lack of accessible solutions for the physically disabled and elderly. Moreover, the effectiveness of home automation is limited by the quality of speech recognition, and its affordability remains a barrier for many. Therefore, there is an increasing demand for an affordable and intelligent assistant for average households.

In today's digital age, Smart Home Automation Systems have evolved to encompass a comprehensive range of technological capabilities that enable seamless and intelligent control of household electrical appliances. These innovative systems have revolutionized the way we live, offering unparalleled convenience, enhanced security, and significant energy efficiency. By leveraging cutting-edge technology, users can effortlessly manage their home environments remotely using computers, smartphones, or voice assistants, ensuring a superior level of comfort and flexibility. The Google Assistant-based home automation framework has been instrumental in popularizing the concept of remote control, allowing users to effortlessly operate home appliances via the internet from anywhere, at any time.

The proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) applications has further underscored the significance of smart home systems in the development of smart cities globally. As we move forward, the need for cost-effective, flexible, and scalable wireless smart home systems that integrate wireless communication and remote control has become increasingly pressing.

However, despite the rapid advancement of technology, there remains a significant gap in accessible solutions for the physically disabled and elderly. The effectiveness of home automation is also limited by the quality of speech recognition, and its affordability remains a significant barrier for many households. Therefore, there is a growing demand for an affordable and intelligent assistant that can cater to the needs of average households, providing a seamless and user-friendly experience. In light of these challenges, our objective is to design a comprehensive and innovative smart home system that addresses the existing limitations, providing a cost-effective, flexible, and scalable solution that integrates wireless communication and remote control. By doing so, we aim to make smart home automation a reality for a broader audience, enhancing the quality of life for individuals from all walks of life.

2. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: Block diagram

The hardware architecture of this system includes a NodeMCU and a smartphone, with wireless communication facilitated via the Internet. In addition to sensors, the system offers multiple methods to alert users of security breaches. One method is a buzzer alarm that emits a loud sound to notify anyone nearby of a security violation. Another method involves sending an email or SMS notification to the registered email address or phone number.

The hardware architecture of the proposed smart home automation system is comprised of two primary components: a NodeMCU (Node MicroController Unit) and a smartphone. The NodeMCU, a microcontroller-based development board, serves as the brain of the system, responsible for processing and executing commands. The smartphone, equipped with internet connectivity, acts as the remote control and monitoring device, enabling users to access and manage their home automation system from anywhere, at any time.

The system's wireless communication is facilitated through the internet, allowing for seamless connectivity and real-time data exchange between the NodeMCU and the smartphone. This enables users to remotely monitor and control their home appliances, receive notifications, and respond to security breaches.

In addition to its core functionality, the system incorporates multiple alert mechanisms to notify users of potential security breaches. These alerts are designed to ensure prompt notification and response to any unauthorized access or suspicious activity. One such method is a buzzer alarm, which emits a loud, attention-grabbing sound to alert anyone in the vicinity of a security violation. This audible alert serves as an immediate warning, allowing individuals to take swift action to address the situation.

Furthermore, the system offers an additional layer of notification through digital means. In the event of a security breach, the system can send an email or SMS notification to the registered email address or phone number, respectively. This ensures that users are informed of any security incidents, even when they are not physically present at the location. This dual-pronged approach provides an added layer of security and peace of mind, allowing users to respond promptly and effectively to potential threats.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed smart home automation system is meticulously designed to ensure comprehensive coverage and real-time monitoring of the entire household. To achieve this, a network of sensors is strategically distributed throughout the house, carefully positioned to capture a wide range of environmental and security-related data. These sensors, equipped with advanced sensing capabilities, continuously collect and transmit real-time data to the central microprocessors, providing a constant stream of information on various parameters such as temperature, humidity, motion detection, and more.

The central microprocessors, serving as the system's brain, are programmed with a sophisticated code that executes a set of predefined functions in a continuous loop. This code, carefully crafted to ensure seamless operation, is responsible for processing the real-time data received from the sensors, analyzing the information, and responding accordingly. The microprocessors' advanced processing capabilities enable rapid analysis and decision-making, allowing the system to respond swiftly to changes in the environment or potential security breaches.

The continuous execution of the uploaded code ensures that the system remains vigilant and proactive, constantly monitoring the environment and responding to any anomalies or deviations from the norm. This real-time monitoring and response capability enables the system to provide an unparalleled level of security, comfort, and convenience, making it an indispensable component of a modern smart home..

Data Collection Unit

The Sensor Module is a crucial component of the Home Automation system, comprising a range of sensors that collect and transmit diverse types of sensor data, including environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, and light intensity, from a specific room or area where the system is implemented. This data is then relayed to a third-party server, such as thingspeak.com, for remote monitoring and visualization, enabling users to access and analyze the data in real-time.

The LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) module is a fundamental component of the system, serving as a visual interface to display critical information, such as system status, sensor readings, and notifications, in a clear and concise manner, thereby enhancing the overall user experience.

Fig.2. LCD Display

ii. **DHT11**: The DHT11 is a cost-effective digital sensor designed to measure environmental temperature and humidity. This electronic device features a capacitive humidity sensing element and a thermistor for detecting moisture, all connected to a high-performance microcontroller.

Fig 3. DHT11

iii. **4 Channel Relay module** - The four-channel relay module consists of four 5V relays, which are electrically operated switches. These relays can be turned on or off using low voltages, such as the 5V supplied by Arduino pins. We utilized this module to connect lights and a fan, as it allows for controlling a high-powered circuit with a low-power signal.

Fig 4 channel relay

iv. **NodeMCU**: This module features a NodeMCU that executes actions based on sensor inputs and user commands. NodeMCU is an open-source IoT platform built on the ESP8266 Wi-Fi SoC, with hardware centered around the ESP-12 module. Typically, "NodeMCU" refers to the firmware rather than the development kit, and this firmware is based on the Lua scripting language.

Fig 5. NodeMCU

4. SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION

- **Google assistant**
- **Blynk app**
- **Adafruit IO**
- **IFTTT Service**

To remotely control home appliances, users can download the Blynk app from the Google Play Store, which simplifies IoT technology. Additionally, Google Assistant can be used to issue voice commands to control the system. IFTTT is employed to link Google Assistant and Adafruit services, allowing for seamless interaction. For example, by saying "Ok Google, turn the light ON" or "OFF," Google Assistant sends the command, which IFTTT then interprets and relays to Adafruit's dashboard, executing the action on the connected device.

Fig 6 Block settings for turning ON and OFF

IFTTT is utilized to link Google Assistant with Adafruit services. By using Google Assistant, you can control the lights in your home with voice commands like "Ok Google, turn the light ON" or "OFF." IFTTT processes the command and sends it to Adafruit’s dashboard, where it is translated into an actionable instruction for the connected device.

Fig.7 Creating Trigger

If This Then That (IFTTT) is a free web-based service that allows users to create chains of simple conditional statements, known as applets. These applets are triggered by changes within other web services like Gmail, Facebook, and Telegram.

The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) is a cross-platform application (available for Windows, macOS, and Linux) written in Java. It is used for writing and uploading programs to Arduino-compatible boards, as well as other development boards supported by third-party cores.

Fig.8 Arduino IDE

"Any phrase can be customized according to the application. The phrases shown in Fig 6.1, which depict trigger fields, are intended for turning the Light ON. To turn the Light OFF, a separate applet with different phrases must be created. Following this, a new page, similar to Fig 3.13, will be displayed, where the user needs to click on the option that connects Google Assistant with Adafruit."

Fig 3.10 Creating IF THIS statement in IFTTT website

Then search for **Google Assistant** and select it.

Fig.9. Searching Google assistant

RESULT ANALYSIS

The output for Google assistant controlled Homeautomation is shown below. Fig 5.1 shows the complete prototype implementation of the proposed system.

Fig. 10.Command to “Turn ON” LIGHT

Fig. 11 Turned ON

Lights and fans can also be remotely controlled using mobile application like Blynk app or tabs or laptops by using the virtual switch on the Blynk platform and also, we can use voice command through the google assistant which can make our project easy. The commands for lighton/off or fan on/off are shown in the figure Fig.3.

When all the sensors are tested together, we get consolidated positive output. The temperature and humidity sensor (DHT11) detects the current temperature and humidity of the room environment is also fed with a threshold of 45 degree Celsius and humidity threshold is set to default 100.

Fig.12 Command given to Turn off LIGHT

Fig. 13 Turned OFF

Fig. 14. Blynk app (switches).

CONCLUSION

This research paper explores home automation using Google Assistant to create an automated home environment. In our project, we have successfully developed a system that can be easily controlled via an Android application or Google Assistant, making it user-friendly and cost-effective. We have successfully implemented a home automation system that allows for easy access and control through remote operation or voice commands. By integrating the Internet of Things (IoT), the home appliances are connected to the internet and can be accessed from anywhere using an Android smartphone with Wi-Fi connectivity.

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